

THE CONCEPT OF FORMAL AND INFORMAL CONVERSATION

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Annotation. The aim of the article is to analyze the role of conversation and its pragmatic features and to consider the definition of the concept of “conversations” and give its classification. As well as analyzes formal and informal conversation.

Formal communication is, typically, conveyed from the top leadership to different departments and employees. Usually, every organization follows a procedure for formal conversation. Think about the annual meetings or even team meetings that your manager calls for. Both formal and informal communication are crucial for maintaining a clear and cordial work culture. As we know it, formal communication is also called official communication. [1,46] Formal communication often follows a specific structure or channels like emails to the clients, whereas informal communication can often flow freely in any direction. Formal meets must maintain secrecy for the messages shared. But when you are having a casual chat, maintaining confidentiality gets tough. Types of formal communication:

Vertical

Here, the communication is held between different organizational levels. So the message is either transferred from the juniors to the group leads to the manager or vice-versa.

Horizontal or lateral

This is the communication that happens between peers from different departments.

Crosswise or diagonal

As the name suggests, here the conversation occurs between two employees working at different levels in different departments. For example, a website developer discussing a project with a sales manager can be categorized as crosswise or diagonal communication.

Types of Informal Communication:

Single strand chain

This is the type of communication where A shares an idea or information with B, who then passes it to C, and D so on....

Cluster chain

Have you ever noticed how a social media challenge becomes viral? People start something unique and tag, say, four friends for the challenge. They complete the challenge and tag three more people each, and so on. That’s how a cluster chain communication is formed and goes on

Gossip chain

Think of the college canteen conversations, where one person vividly describes her recent adventures to a group of friends gathered around the table to listen. That’s how the gossip chain works. One person initiates the conversation and shares information with a group of people, who then pass on the information to more people.[3,178]

In these days most organizations attempt to efficiently blend formal and informal communication channels. The result is improved efficiency, productivity, and trust among the employees. Effective communication skills play a crucial role in advancing anyone's career, from a fresher to a team leader to a manager. The PREP method has four stages: P or Point or stating the main point briefly; R or Reason or providing reasons to substantiate the point; E or Example or Evidence or providing examples to validate the reasons, and P or Point or adding a concluding point while re-emphasizing the main point.

The Greek philosopher Aristotle's three appeals of Logos, Ethos, and Pathos hold the secret to being a persuasive speaker and get the right message across. Logos or appealing to the listener's logic, Ethos, or the appeal of the speaker's credibility, and Pathos, or emotional appeal, help one to be an effective speaker.

Add the Active Listening course to the bouquet and you will be set. So make the most of this work-from-home period and master the skills of effective communication. [2,157]

Importance Of Formal Communication At The Workplace

Being formal, clear, specific and using correct grammar are some of the most important things when it comes to office communications. It is a skill to know when to use the language required for different situations, as well as be a proper judge of etiquette and mannerisms as and when required on the spot.

Advantages of using formal communication at workplace:

1. Authority: Formal communication ensures a proper channel of information flow between the superior and their corresponding subordinates. This results in a clear establishment of line of authority and workflow. Making responsibilities clear for subordinates is very efficient in this way of communication.
2. Effective and clear communication: The communication is a direct transfer of data between the managers, staffs and the organization. This brings clarity to the responsibility and what is expected of them for the welfare of the organization. This also establishes clarity on when and where information download is required to perform work
3. Order of information flow: This form of communication establishes an orderly information flow. Working on an environment where the information flow is from different places in an unordered manner creates ruckus and chaos. This brings down the efficiency of the work. Maintaining a formal communication helps in having an orderly information flow as the line of superiority is established in this method.
4. Single source of information: The job of the employee is solely dependent on the cross functional support and the information flow between the groups Any decision and results are based on the information received. [4,212]

To conclude, having the necessary skills to maintain a professional dialogue in the workplace and knowing when and when not to use facts, jargon, technical terms, style, and informal elements is a vital part of the all-round development and performance of the employee. It is therefore necessary to stress the importance of all workers having this valuable skill, and enforcing the rule of corporate communication in the workplace.

References:

1. Couper-Kuhlen E, Selting M (eds.) 1996 Prosody in Conversation. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK6. -P.46

2. Drew P, Heritage J (eds.) 1992 Talk at Work. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK7. -P. 157.
3. Goffman E 1983 The interaction order. American Sociological. Review 48: -P.178.
4. Goodwin C 1981 Conversational Organization: Interaction Between Speakers and Hearers. Academic Press, New York. -P. 212.

